

Acupuncture, Moxibustion and Phytotherapy on the treatment of Female Infertility: A Scoping Review.

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Abstract: Background: Infertility, characterized by the inability to conceive through natural means, poses substantial medical, psychosocial, and economic challenges. Conventional treatments, including medication and assisted reproductive technologies, often entail adverse effects and financial burdens.

Objective: The aim of this review is to identify, examine, and summarize available evidence about the treatment of female infertility with acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy, and identify gaps in knowledge and research, in order to improve future studies and female infertility management.

Results: For this review six databases were searched. Nine randomized controlled trials published between 2017 and 2022 were included, totalling 1440 participants. The interventions demonstrated efficacy, particularly in cases of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, through improvements in pregnancy rates, hormonal balance, and quality of life. The therapeutic approaches were phytotherapy (n=4), acupuncture (n=3), acupuncture and phytotherapy (n=1) and moxibustion (n=1). Two of the studies that used only phytotherapy had a higher pregnancy rate. There was a higher pregnancy rate in the combined therapy group (letrozole + electroacupuncture combined with ginger-isolated moxibustion). The study that combined phytotherapy with acupuncture showed a higher pregnancy rate compared to the sham acupuncture group. In the moxibustion study, there was a higher pregnancy rate in the observational group (moxibustion + clomiphene citrate) compared to the control group (clomiphene citrate). However, methodological limitations, small samples, and short study durations highlight the need for more rigorous research. Customization based on menstrual cycle stages emerged as a critical consideration.

Conclusion: Acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy, when integrated with conventional treatments, holds the potential for enhancing fertility outcomes, emphasizing the importance of a patient-centred, individualized approach.

Keywords: Female Fertility; Female Infertility; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture; Herbal Medicine; Moxibustion.

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1. Introduction

Infertility refers to the inability of an individual to conceive through natural means. In general, this condition is not the typical state for a healthy adult ^{1,2}. Specifically, female infertility is defined as the inability of a woman to become pregnant after one year of regular unprotected sexual intercourse ³. It is a multifaceted disorder with considerable medical, psychosocial, and economic implications ⁴.

The escalating number of infertility cases places a substantial economic burden, with medical expenses rising annually. According to the World Health Organization ⁵, female

infertility is a global health concern, affecting not only the overall fertility rate but also the population growth rate.

Female infertility can stem from various factors, including menstrual abnormalities, endometriosis, pelvic adhesions, ovulatory disorders, tubal blockage, hyperprolactinemia, and uterine abnormalities^{5,6}. Specific conditions like congenital gonadal dysgenesis, hyperprolactinemia, decreased ovarian reserve (DOR), polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), luteinized unruptured follicle syndrome (LUFS), and chronic anovulation are main contributors to infertility⁷.

Common therapeutic methods for infertility include medical treatments and complementary and alternative medicine (CAM)⁸. Medical treatments may involve fertility medications, surgery, in vitro fertilization (IVF), or other assisted reproductive technologies (ART)⁹⁻¹². Medications used in clinic commonly include clomiphene citrate (CC), human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), human menopausal gonadotropin (hMG), gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), GnRH analogs, bromocriptine, and cabergoline¹³⁻¹⁹.

However, these medications have various physical and psychological adverse reactions, such as breast tenderness, swelling, rash, mood swings, depression, nausea, vomiting, headache, bone density loss and so on^{20,21}. Furthermore, IVF treatment is expensive, emotionally, and financially, for both the patients and the public²². In light of this, there is a pressing need for alternative approaches, such as Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM).

Originating in ancient China and spanning over 5000 years, TCM is grounded in philosophical principles like *Yin-Yang* and *Qi-blood*, the Five Elements, Meridian system, and *Zang Fu* organ theory²³.

Yin-Yang symbolizes two opposing yet interconnected forces that harmoniously balance to maintain homeostasis. An imbalance in *Yin* and *Yang* disrupts this equilibrium, leading to the onset and progression of diseases²³.

TCM encompasses traditional therapies like acupuncture, herbal medicine, moxibustion, *tui na*, and *qigong*²⁴⁻²⁹.

Several studies have explored the impact of various TCM methods on infertility, showing effectiveness in improving fertility indicators such as endometrial receptivity, oocyte and embryo quality, pregnancy rate, hormone levels, ovarian reserve, and menstrual conditions and symptoms³⁰⁻³⁵.

However, to ensure the reliability, quality, and precision of these findings, more robust research is essential. Many studies focus on specific pathologies and fertility indicators without necessarily establishing the true effectiveness of TCM in terms of pregnancy and birth rates, often lacking adequate duration and follow-up. Additionally, understanding how different TCM techniques can be used alone or in combination to enhance outcomes is crucial.

This scoping review aims to systematically identify, examine, and summarize existing evidence on the treatment of female infertility with acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy. It seeks to identify knowledge gaps, improve future studies, and explore more effective approaches to managing female infertility. The research questions guiding this review are: (1) Which of these TCM methods are more commonly used for infertility treatment and their associated pregnancy rates?; (2) What is the overall effectiveness of these TCM methods in addressing infertility?; (3) Are there benefits to combining different TCM methods for female infertility treatment?; (4) Which acupoints are most commonly used for female infertility treatment, and what is their efficacy?; and (5) Which plants are frequently used for female infertility treatment, and what is their efficacy?

2. Methods

2.1. Protocol and registration

A scoping review is a form of knowledge synthesis that employs a systematic approach to chart existing evidence on a particular topic, aiming to identify key concepts, theories, sources, and areas of knowledge gaps³⁶.

For our scoping review, we followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist. To ensure transparency and accountability, we performed a pre-registration of the review, which was thoroughly reviewed by our research team and conducted on Open Science Framework on August 20, 2022.

2.2. Eligibility criteria

In our review, we considered studies that met the following inclusion criteria: they were published between 2017 and 2022; classified as Clinical Trials or Randomized Controlled Trials; written in either English or Portuguese; included female participants diagnosed with infertility according to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines; and had female pregnancy and/or live births as the primary outcome. To ensure that the treatment outcomes were not influenced by IVF, studies involving women undergoing IVF were excluded from our analysis.

2.3. Information sources, Literature search and Selection of sources of evidence

A comprehensive search was conducted across six electronic databases, including PubMed, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, SciELO, LILACS, Science Direct, and Web of Science. The protocol was devised by the research team and can be accessed in OSF (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/42MA7>). The keywords used were: ((*female fertility*) OR (*female infertility*)) AND ((*acupuncture*) OR (*herbal medicine*) OR (*moxibustion*) OR (*Chinese traditional medicine*)).

The search results were exported to Rayyan³⁷, where duplicates were removed by one of the team researchers. Two reviewers from the team independently screened the same 228 publications directly within Rayyan, evaluating titles, abstracts, and subsequently the full text of each publication. In instances of discrepancies regarding study selection and data extraction, consensus was reached through discussions between the reviewers, and involvement of other team members was sought if required.

2.4. Data charting

Two reviewers from the research team collaborated to create a data-charting form, which was used to assess the eligibility of the selected studies for the review and to identify the relevant variables to be extracted. Independently, the two reviewers charted the data from the selected studies, then engaged in discussions to compare their findings and ensure accuracy. Throughout the process, the data-charting form was regularly updated in an iterative manner to incorporate new insights and maintain coherence.

2.5. Data items

Data abstraction was performed, covering the following aspects: author, year of publication, research aim, sample size, specific infertility pathology, utilized treatments (acupuncture, phytotherapy, moxibustion, or a combination of acupuncture and phytotherapy), evaluated parameters, acupoints and/or plants used in the treatments, main findings, and study quality.

To assess the study quality, we employed the Downs and Black Scale. This checklist provides a comprehensive critical appraisal tool suitable for public health practitioners, policy-makers, and decision-makers. It offers a step-by-step and user-friendly assessment applicable to all quantitative study methodologies.

For this purpose, we utilized the revised version of the Downs *et al.*³⁸ checklist, which is specifically designed to evaluate the methodological quality of randomized studies in the field of health care interventions.

2.6. Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence

The Downs and Black Scale comprises 27 questions that assess various aspects of study quality, including reporting quality (10 questions), external validity (3 questions), internal validity (bias and confounding) (13 questions), and statistical power (1 question). Internal consistency for the total score and all subscales has been shown to be high (Kuder-Richardson 20 test: 0.89), except for external validity (0.54). The reliability of the subscales ranges from "good" for bias to "poor" for external validity³⁸.

The original scale yields a total score out of 32 points, with one question in the reporting section carrying a possible two points and the statistical power question carrying a possible five points. In some studies, researchers have used a modified version of the scale by simplifying the power question. In this modified version, a single point is awarded if a study had sufficient statistical power to detect a clinically significant effect, indicated by a probability value of less than 5% for a difference being due to chance³⁹.

The modified version which we employed in this study therefore has a maximum score of 28. Each paper was assigned a grade of "excellent" (24–28 points), "good" (19–23 points), "fair" (14–18 points) or "poor" (<14 points).

2.7. Synthesis of data collection

The data were continuously charted in interactive tables, facilitating ongoing updates and revisions. These tables were shared among the review team members, fostering collaboration and enabling a comprehensive synthesis of the findings. Through regular discussions and exchanges, the team worked together to analyze and interpret the data effectively.

3. Results

For this scoping review, a thorough search was conducted across six databases, resulting in a total of 308 articles and 1440 participants. Through a series of selection stages, the research team narrowed down the articles, eventually retaining nine that met the inclusion criteria. The entire process, including the reasons for exclusions at each stage and the final selections, is illustrated in detail in Figure 1.

As it can be observed in Table 1, amongst the final nine articles, four of them focused on phytotherapy as a treatment modality⁴⁰⁻⁴³. Three articles centered around acupuncture⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶, one article explored the combined use of acupuncture and phytotherapy⁴⁷, and one article investigated the effectiveness of moxibustion⁴⁸. Notably, some studies incorporated electroacupuncture in their treatment protocols^{45,46}.

As reported in Table 2, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) emerged as the most commonly discussed pathology, featuring in five out of the nine articles^{40,45-48}. However, other pathologies were also addressed in the selected studies. These included Decreased Ovarian Reserve (DOR)⁴¹, hyperprolactinemic Infertility⁴², Premature Ovarian Aging (POA)⁴³, and Premature Ovarian Failure (POF) of autoimmune etiology⁴⁴.

The average sample size across the nine studies was approximately 160 participants, although this number was somewhat influenced by one article with a larger sample size of 926 women⁴⁶. Excluding this study, the average sample size would be around 64 participants. The smallest sample size in any study was 24, while the largest was 926. Overall, the nine studies involved a total of 1440 female participants, ranging in age from 18 to 40 years.

Regarding the location of the studies, the majority of them (n=6) were conducted in China^{41,42,45-48}. Two studies were conducted in Iran^{40,43}, and one study was carried out in Egypt⁴⁴. The studies were primarily conducted in hospital facilities, with the exception of one study that took place at a university⁴⁴.

Figure 1. Flow Diagram.

All nine articles in this scoping review utilized the same study design - they were all randomized controlled trials (RCTs). This commonality was expected, as one of the inclusion criteria for the review was to include RCTs or clinical trials. Reported in Table 1, among the selected studies, three were single-blind RCTs ^{40,41,47}, one was a double-blind RCT ⁴³, and another had a combination of single-blind (active vs. control acupuncture) in two groups and double-blind (clomiphene vs. placebo) in two other groups ⁴⁶. The remaining four studies were non-blinded RCTs ^{42,44,45,48}.

Table 1. Techniques, study design and quality of the included research.

Method	Authorship	Study design	Sample Size	Study Quality
Phytotherapy (n=4)	Ainehchi <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	Single-blind randomized clinical trial	60	Good
	Duan <i>et al.</i> ⁴¹	Prospective, randomized-controlled trial	80	Good
	Feng <i>et al.</i> ⁴²	Pilot randomized controlled trial	77	Good
Acupuncture (n=3)	Hosseini-Rashidi <i>et al.</i> ⁴³	Randomized, placebo-controlled clinical double-blind trial	61	Excellent
	Dawood <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁴	Pilot, non-blinded, randomized controlled trial.	24	Good
	Qiu-Ping <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁹	Randomized controlled trial.	65	Good
Acupuncture + Phytotherapy (n=1)	Wu <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁶	Randomized, multicenter, clinical double-blind (clomiphene vs. placebo) and single-blind (active vs. control acupuncture) trial.	926	Excellent
	Pan <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁷	Randomized, sham-controlled single-blind (patients, outcome assessors, data collectors, and statisticians) trial.	79	Excellent
Moxibustion (n=1)	Ye <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁸	Randomized controlled trial.	68	Good

Regarding the details of the TCM treatments, such as the duration of each session (e.g., time of needle retention) or the overall duration of therapy and dosages, some articles lacked clarity or omitted this information ^{40,42-44,46-48}. Based on the available data, the average total treatment time mentioned in each article was approximately 3.56 months or menstrual cycles. Despite some inconsistencies in reporting, this average duration provides an overall understanding of the treatment periods across the selected studies.

Table 2. Characteristics and methodology of the included studies.

Authorship	Cause of infertility	Objective	Acupuncture points or Plants Used	Evaluated Parameters
Ainehchi <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)	To evaluate the effect of herbal mixture alone and combined with clomiphene on serum antioxidants, glycemic status, menstrual regulation, and pregnancy rate	<i>Mentha spicata</i> 250 mg, <i>Zingiber officinale</i> 200 mg, <i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i> 150 mg, and <i>Citrus sinensis</i> 100 mg	Pregnancy rate; serum antioxidants; glycemic status; menstrual regulation.
Duan <i>et al.</i> ⁴¹	Decreased ovarian reserve (DOR)	To evaluate the effect of sequential therapy for Kidney-tonifying with TCM on improving the fecundity and quality of life.	Zhuyun Tang and Guchong Tang Zhuyun Tang: <i>Semen cuscutae</i> 12-30 g, <i>Fructus lycii</i> 15 g, <i>Fructus rubi</i> 15 g, <i>Morinda officinalis</i> 12 g, <i>Herba epimedii</i> 10 g, <i>Cornu cervi</i> 10 g, <i>Radix dipsaci</i> 10 g, <i>Cortex eucommiae</i> 12 g, <i>Mulberry</i> 15 g, <i>Polygonum multiflorum</i> 10-20 g, <i>Fluoriturum</i> 30 g, <i>Angelica biserrata</i> 6 g. Guchong Tang: <i>Semen cuscutae</i> 12-30 g, <i>Fructus lycii</i> 12-20 g, <i>Fructus rubi</i> 12-20 g, <i>Morinda officinalis</i> 12 g, <i>Herba epimedii</i> 10 g, <i>Cornu cervi</i> 10 g, <i>Radix dipsaci</i> 12 g, <i>Cortex eucommiae</i> 10 g, <i>Eclipta prostrata</i> 20 g, <i>Fructus ligustri lucidi</i> 10-20 g, <i>Rhizoma dioscoreae</i> 15 g	Kupperman indices; hormone levels; ovarian reserve functions; questionnaire (MENQOL) scores; pregnancy rate.
Feng <i>et al.</i> ⁴²	Hyperprolactinemic infertility	To evaluate the effect of bu-shen-zhu-yun decoction combined with bromocriptine on	Bu-shen-zhu-yun decoction: Deer horn slices 10 g,	Prolactin (PRL) and kisspeptin (KP) serum indexes; anxiety self-assessment scale (SAS) and insomnia severity index

		serum hormones, anxiety, and pregnancy rate.	Violet quartz 10 g, dens <i>draconis</i> 20 g; <i>Radix paeoniae alba</i> 12 g, fried <i>Rizhoma discoriae</i> 18 g, vine-gared <i>Radix bupleuri</i> 9 g, <i>Radix salviae miltiorrhizae</i> 10 g, Gambir plant 10 g, <i>Semen cuscutae</i> 18 g, <i>Fructus corni</i> 12 g	scale (ISI) scores; pregnancy rate.
Hossein-Rashidi <i>et al.</i> ⁴³	Premature ovarian aging (POA)	To evaluate the effects of vitex agnus-castus extract on fertility, secretory functions of the pituitary-gonadal axis, and reproductive potential.	The decoction was mixed and taken orally twice daily (morning and evening) but suspended during menstruation. <i>Vitex agnus-castus</i> (VAC) extract - 40 drops of VAC (80-90 mg of fruit per milliliter extract) orally in the morning on an empty stomach for 4 months throughout the follicular phase.	Ovulation days; endometrial thickness; serum concentrations of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), anti-mullerian hormone (AMH), and estradiol (E2); the average time of serum positive β -HCG test; chemical and clinical pregnancy rates.
Dawood <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁴	Premature ovarian failure (POF) of autoimmune etiology	To evaluate the efficacy of live bee stings at fertility points and acupuncture in treating symptoms and managing infertility.	Epangxian II, GV26 (Shuigou), EX-HN 3, LR 14 (Qimen), CV 14 (Juque), CV 12 (Zhongwan), KI 16 (Huangshu), CV 6 (Qihai), CV 19 (Zigong), CV 4 (Guanyuan), CV 3 (Zhongji), ST 30 (Qichong), BL44 (Shentang), BL15 (Xinshu), BL17 (Geshu), BL23 (Shenshu), BL31 (Shangliao), BL32 (Ciliao), BL33 (Zhongliao), LI4 (Hegu), GB 30 (Huantiao), and BL60 (Kunlun).	Serum concentrations of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), estradiol (E2), and anti-mullerian hormone (AMH); frequency and percentage of rheumatoid factor, antithyroid antibodies, lupus antibodies, and anti-ovarian antibodies; menopausal, psychological, and sex-related symptoms; ultrasound to assess antral follicle count and ovarian volume; pregnancy rate.
Qiu-Ping <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁹	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)	To evaluate the effect of electro-acupuncture combined with ginger-isolated moxibustion on endometrial receptivity.	Acupuncture in menstrual period: EX-CA1 (Electroacupuncture (EA)), ST29 (EA), SP6, LR3, and LI4; Acupuncture in follicular phase: CV6, KI12 (EA), Luanchao (extra, ovary) (EA), SP6 (EA), ST36 (EA), and KI3; ginger-isolated moxibustion: CV4 and CV8; Acupuncture in the ovulatory period: Luanchao (extra, ovary) (EA), GB27 (EA), CV6 (EA), CV3 (EA), SP10 (EA), SP6 (EA), LI4, and LR3; Acupuncture in luteal phase: EX-CA1 (EA), SP10 (EA), ST36 (EA), SP6, and KI3; ginger-isolated moxibustion CV4.	Symptom score of TCM; endometrial thickness and morphology; the number of ovulation cycles; bilateral uterine artery pulsatility index (PI); resistance index (RI); the sum of peak systolic velocity/end diastolic velocity (S/D); pregnancy rate.
Wu <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁶	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)	To evaluate if active acupuncture, alone or combined with clomiphene, increases the number of live births.	Active acupuncture protocol 1: GV20, CV6, CV3, bilateral ST29, bilateral SP9, bilateral SP6, and bilateral LI4 (all connected to an electrical stimulator, except the GV20 and bilateral LI4); Active acupuncture protocol 2: GV20, CV6, CV3, bilateral ST25, bilateral ST29, bilateral PC6, bilateral SP6, and bilateral LR3 (bilateral ST25, bilateral ST29, bilateral SP6, and bilateral LR3, were connected to an electrical stimulator).	Primary outcome: live birth. Secondary outcomes: ovulation; conception; pregnancy, pregnancy loss; multiple pregnancies; anthropometrics; hirsutism; acne; hormonal changes (progesterone, total testosterone, estradiol, and sex hormone-binding globulin);

				quality-of-life scores (Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Health-Related Quality of Life Questionnaire; Chinese Quality of Life Instrument; Medical Outcomes Study 36-Item Short Form Health Survey; Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale; Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale); adverse events.
Pan <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁷	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)	To evaluate the efficacy of acupuncture combined with herbal medicine.	Phytotherapy: Taohong siwu decoction (in menstrual period); Bushen tiaojing decoction (non-menstrual periods for Spleen-Kidney Yang deficiency); guishao dihuang decoction (non-menstrual periods for Liver-Kidney deficiency). Acupuncture (13 points maximum): - Main points: RN4, bilateral EX- CA1, ST29, ST36, and SP6. - Points selected based on the syndrome differentiation and the menstrual cycle: RN6, RN12, DU20, bilateral ST25, KI3, KI6, LR3, SP10, and PC6.	Primary outcome: pregnancy rate. Secondary outcomes: ovulation rate; PCOS and TCM syndrome scores; serum sex hormone levels like estradiol (E2), testosterone (T), progesterone (P), luteinizing hormone (LH), and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH); insulin resistance index.
Ye <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁸	Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)	To evaluate the effects and related mechanism of heat-sensitive moxibustion combined with clomiphene citrate capsules for infertility.	Heat-sensitive moxibustion at the points: CV4 and bilateral EX-CA1, SP10, and BL23.	Endometrial thickness; ovarian volume; levels of serum sex hormones (testosterone (T), luteinizing hormone (LH), estradiol (E2)); tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B); pregnancy rate.

Follow-up time (reported in Table 3) was mentioned in all of the studies except for Qiu-Ping *et al.* ⁴⁵. Across the remaining articles, the average follow-up duration was approximately 8.88 months. This follow-up period allowed researchers to observe the effects of the TCM treatments on the participants' fertility outcomes over an extended period of time. The varying follow-up durations provide valuable insights into the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of the treatments in addressing female infertility.

Indeed, the results of the selected studies exhibited some variability, reflecting the diversity of TCM treatments and the different infertility pathologies investigated. However, certain parameters were consistently evaluated across multiple studies, providing valuable insights into treatment outcomes. One such universal parameter was the rate of female pregnancy and/or live births, which was a crucial eligibility criterion for our review. This direct and objective measure served as a clear indicator of treatment effectiveness and was easy to interpret.

Additionally, several other commonly assessed parameters included hormone levels such as testosterone, luteinizing hormone, estradiol, follicle-stimulating hormone, and/or anti-mullerian hormone. These hormone levels play a pivotal role in the regulation of the reproductive system and provide crucial insights into the hormonal status of the participants during treatment ⁵⁰⁻⁵².

Furthermore, endometrial thickness and ovulation were frequently monitored to gauge the effects of the TCM interventions on the participants' reproductive health. These

measures were particularly relevant for assessing improvements in the uterine environment and the regularity of ovulation, both essential factors for successful conception⁵³⁻⁵⁶.

Table 3. Groups of study, timeline and follow-up.

Authorship	Group of study	Timeline	Follow-up
Ainehchi <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	Group 1 – Clomiphene citrate (50-150 mg) Group 2 – Herbal mixture (700 mg) Group 3 – Clomiphene citrate (50-150 mg) with herbal mixture (700 mg)	The administration started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle and continued for 5 days, for 3 menstrual cycles. Daily. Clomiphene citrate administration started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle and continued for 5 days, for 3 menstrual cycles; herbal mixture daily; for 3 months.	9 months
Dawood <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁴	Group I – Acupuncture Group II – Bee stings	Once every other day, 3 sessions per week – alternating between the points in the frontal region with the dorsal region, for 3 months. 2 sessions per week (15 minutes each) – in fertility points on the back and abdomen, 3 to 6 stings per session, for 3 months.	1 year after treatment
Duan <i>et al.</i> ⁴¹	Control group - Estrogen (1 mg/time) and progesterone (dydrogesterone) (10 mg/time) Test group – Zhuyun tang (157-185 g) and guchong tang (135-179 g)	Estrogen started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle and continued for 21 days, once a day; dydrogesterone started on the twelfth day and continued for 10 days, 2 times per day; for 3 menstrual cycles. Zhuyun tang started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle and continued for 10 days, once a day; guchong tang started on the fifteenth day and continued for 12 days, once a day; for 3 menstrual cycles.	1 year
Feng <i>et al.</i> ⁴²	Control group – Bromocriptine (2,5-3,75 mg/day to 10-20 mg/day) Observation group – Bromocriptine (2,5-3,75 mg/day to 10-20 mg/day) and bu-shen-zhu-yun decoction (129 g)	The administration started after menstruation, 2 to 3 doses per day (the dosage was increasing according to the diagnosis), for 3 months. Bromocriptine started after menstruation, 2 to 3 doses per day (the dosage was increasing according to the diagnosis); the decoction was taken twice a day and was suspended during menstruation; for 3 months.	6 months
Qiu-Ping <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁹	Western medication group – Letrozole (5 mg/day) Combined therapy group – Letrozole (5 mg/day) and electroacupuncture with ginger isolated moxibustion	The administration started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, and continued for 5 days, once per day, for 3 menstrual cycles. Letrozole started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, and continued for 5 days, once per day; electroacupuncture and moxibustion were made on the menstrual period, follicular phase, ovulatory period, and luteal phase in different acupoints, once every two days, 30 minutes each time; for 3 menstrual cycles.	N/A
Pan <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁷	Manual acupuncture group – Herbal medication with manual acupuncture Sham acupuncture group – Herbal medication with sham acupuncture	Herbal medication was taohong siwu decoction on menstrual period, and on non-menstrual period it was bushen tiaojing decoction or guishao dihuang decoction, according to the diagnostic, 2 times per day; acupuncture was made 2 times at a week for 30 minutes each session (no more than 13 acupoints at a time); the treatments started on the third day of menstrual cycle and continued until the third day after ovulation; for 3 menstrual cycles. Herbal medication was taohong siwu decoction on menstrual period, and on non-menstrual period it was bushen tiaojing decoction or guishao dihuang decoction, according to the diagnostic, 2 times per day; acupuncture was made 2 times at a week for 30 minutes each session (no more than 13 acupoints at a time); the treatments started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, and continued until the third day after ovulation; for 3 menstrual cycles.	24 weeks after treatment
Wu <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁶	Group 1 – Active acupuncture (maximum 32 treatments) plus clomiphene citrate (maximum 150 mg/day or 750 mg/cycle)	Active acupuncture (deep needle with manual and electrical stimulation every 10 minutes), was 2 times per week started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, 30 minutes each session; 1 pill of clomiphene citrate (50 mg) started on the third day of the menstrual cycle and continued until the seventh day (5 days), for 4 cycles (if ovulation didn't occur, the dose was increased to one more pill, the maximum dose being 150 mg per day	10 months after treatment

	Group 2 – Control acupuncture (maximum 32 treatments) plus clomiphene citrate (maximum 150 mg/day or 750 mg/cycle)	or 750 per cycle) (patients who didn't menstruate took medroxyprogesterone acetate (5 mg/day) for 10 days, to induce withdrawal bleeding). Control acupuncture (superficial needle and no stimulation, just mock electricity) was 2 times per week, started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, 30 minutes each session; 1 pill of clomiphene citrate (50 mg) started on the third day of the menstrual cycle and continued until the seventh day (5 days), for 4 cycles (if ovulation didn't occur, the dose was increased to one more pill, the maximum dose being 150 mg per day or 750 per cycle) (patients who didn't menstruate took medroxyprogesterone acetate (5 mg/day) for 10 days, to induce withdrawal bleeding).	
	Group 3 – Active acupuncture (maximum 32 treatments) plus placebo	Active acupuncture (deep needle with manual and electrical stimulation every 10 minutes), was 2 times per week started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, 30 minutes each session; 1 pill of placebo started on the third day of the menstrual cycle and continued until the seventh day (5 days), for 4 cycles (patients who didn't menstruate took medroxyprogesterone acetate (5 mg/day) for 10 days, to induce withdrawal bleeding).	
	Group 4 – Control acupuncture (maximum 32 treatments) plus placebo	Control acupuncture (superficial needle and no stimulation, just mock electricity) was 2 times per week, started on the third day of the menstrual cycle, 30 minutes each session; 1 pill of placebo started on the third day of the menstrual cycle and continued until the seventh day (5 days), for 4 cycles (patients who didn't menstruate took medroxyprogesterone acetate (5 mg/day) for 10 days, to induce withdrawal bleeding).	
Hossein-Rashidi <i>et al.</i> 43	Control group – Letrozole (1 pill - 5 mg)	The administration started on the third day of the menstrual cycle and continued for 4 days; when the follicle reached 18-20 mm, the patient received 10,000 IU of human chorionic gonadotropin (HCG) intramuscularly.	4 months
	Experimental group - Vitex agnus-castus extract (VAC) (80-90 mg of fruit/ml extract)	Administration of 40 drops of VAC throughout the follicular phase, for 4 months.	
Ye <i>et al.</i> 48	Control group – Clomiphene citrate capsules (50 mg/time)	The administration started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle, and continued for 5 days, once a day, for 6 menstrual cycles.	1 year after treatment
	Observation group – Clomiphene citrate capsules (50 mg/time) and heat-sensitive moxibustion	Clomiphene started on the fifth day of the menstrual cycle, and continued for 5 days, once a day; heat-sensitive moxibustion on alternate days (after the patient felt heat-sensitive (heat-sensitive point) moxibustion was performed at this point for another 10 minutes until the heat sensitization disappeared).	

Interestingly, some studies went beyond solely evaluating physical parameters and also assessed patients' quality of life using various methods ^{41,42,44,46}. This approach is highly relevant as infertility can profoundly affect individuals' mental and emotional well-being ⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. Evaluating the quality of life of the participants provided a more comprehensive understanding of how these TCM treatments can address not only the physical aspects of infertility but also its psychosocial effects. This holistic approach acknowledges the complex relationship between infertility and quality of life, emphasizing the importance of addressing both aspects to achieve successful outcomes in infertility management.

The reporting of side effects associated with the treatments varied among the studies. In some articles, the side effects were not mentioned ^{42,46}. On the other hand, in several studies, no adverse reactions were reported ^{40,47,48}, or they were not specifically identified in the article ⁴⁵. Moreover, in the studies where side effects were reported, they were mostly not statistically significant ^{41,44}.

After analyzing the articles, it became evident that some conventional therapies were used in several of the studies. Three of these conventional therapies were particularly

noteworthy: bromocriptine, clomiphene citrate, and letrozole. Table 1 provides a brief analysis of the use and significance of these conventional therapies, shedding light on their role and effectiveness in the management of female infertility.

Table 4. Conventional therapies.

Conventional therapies	Bromocriptine	Clomiphene citrate	Letrozole
Studies where they were used	Feng et al. 42.	Ainehchi et al. 40, Wu et al. 46, Ye et al. 48	Hossein-Rashidi et al. 43, Qiu-Ping et al. 49.
Designation	It acts as a dopamine receptor, controlling the levels of prolactin and sex hormones, and having an effect on ovulation and the menstrual cycle Feng et al. 42.	It binds to estrogen receptors and suppresses endometrial estrogen. It increases endometrial thickening, stimulates ovulation and the secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (Ainehchi et al., 2019).	It is an aromatase inhibitor (an enzyme that converts testosterone into estrogen), promotes ovulation (Amer et al., 2017).
Situations/pathologies in which it is normally used	Hyperprolactinemia Feng et al. 42.	It is a first-line treatment to induce ovulation in Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS). Also indicated in other situations where it is necessary to increase LH and FSH gonadotropin levels Ainehchi et al., 2019; Tie-Jun Ye; Hong-Xia Cheng, 2020; Wu et al., 2017).	Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) (Lin et al., 2022).
Common side effects	Nausea, vomiting, vertigo and somnolence. There are other side effects more serious, but they are not so common Feng et al. 42.	Anovulation rate 23.4%, live birth rate 19.1%, and multiple pregnancy rate 7.4% after 5 months of therapy. Dysmenorrhea and excessive enlargement of the ovaries and formation of ovarian cysts (Pan et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2017).	Low pregnancy rate and high early miscarriage rate. Very common adverse effects: hypercholesterolemia, hot flushes, hyperhidrosis, arthralgia, fatigue, and asthenia, among many others (Lin et al., 2022; Mejia et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022).

4. Discussion

The current scoping review provides insights into the evidence of acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy techniques for treating infertility. This scoping review uncovered that phytotherapy, acupuncture, moxibustion, and electroacupuncture are commonly employed TCM methods for treating infertility.

4.1. Acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy in pregnancy rates

Overall, the studies provided justifications for the effectiveness of these TCM methods in infertility treatment, revealing higher pregnancy rates ($p < 0.05$) in groups that utilized these methods compared to those relying solely on medication. The main results of these studies are depicted in Table 5.

However, the results of Dawood *et al.*⁴⁴ and Wu *et al.*⁴⁶ studies indicated that acupuncture might not be as effective as other methods in increasing pregnancy rates. This discrepancy could be attributed to the lack of adaptation of acupuncture protocols to the menstrual cycle of women. Moreover, it is essential to consider that although clomiphene appears to be more effective than acupuncture in enhancing pregnancy rates according to the Wu *et al.*'s study, its usage may be limited due to associated side effects. For example, a systematic review⁶⁰ showed evidence of significant effectiveness of acupuncture intervention for infertile women without undergoing assisted reproductive techniques in pregnancy rate, ovulation rate, LH, and endometrial thickness compared with control group

(that only used standard therapies, such as injected Western drugs and oral Western medication).

Table 5. Main results of the included studies.

Authorship	Main results
	The ultrasound showed no significant differences after treatment in the number and size of follicles and the size of the ovaries.
	The oligomenorrhea rate was reduced in all groups after treatment.
Ainehchi et al. ⁴⁰	The group where more women were ovulating and becoming pregnant was the group where the herbal mixture was given along with clomiphene citrate (17 women had dominant follicles and 5 of them became pregnant); against the group where only the herbal mixture was given, 11 women had dominant follicles and 2 of them became pregnant. Total: 11 pregnancies. Group 1= 4 (20%); Group 2= 2 (10%); Group 3= 5 (25%) In the 3 groups, there was a regulation of the menstrual cycle, ovulation, and pregnancy.
	The levels of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH) and ovarian stromal resistance index decreased significantly in the group that received the phytotherapy (test group) ($P<0.001$).
Duan et al. ⁴¹	Levels of estradiol (E2), anti-mullerian hormone (AMH), mid-luteal phase E2, progesterone, antral follicular count, and ovarian diameter increased significantly in the test group ($P<0.001$). Quality of life significantly improved in the test group compared to the control group (Kupperman indices and MENQOL scores were lower in the test group) ($P<0.001$). The pregnancy rate was higher in the test group (19 pregnancies versus 10 in the control group) ($P<0.05$).
	Serum levels of PRL, SAS, and ISI scores were significantly lower in the observation group (bu-shen-zhu-yun decoction combined with bromocriptine) than in the control group (bromocriptine) ($P<0.05$).
Feng et al. ⁴²	The pregnancy rate was higher in the observation group ($P=0.031$) where there were also fewer early miscarriages ($P=0.015$). Observation group: 25 successful pregnancies, 4 cases of early miscarriage, and 3 cases of serious adverse reactions. Control group: 14 successful pregnancies, 12 early miscarriages, and 9 cases of serious adverse reactions.
	The AMH levels increased in both groups, but after four months were higher in the experimental group (VAC) ($P<0.05$).
Hossein-Rashidi et al. ⁴³	In the experimental group, the concentration of FSH and E2 were significantly decreased, as well as the levels of E2 on ovulation day and the average time of serum positive β -HCG test ($P<0.05$). In the group receiving VAC, ovulation day ($P=0.001$), endometrial thickness ($P<0.05$), chemical and clinical pregnancy rates were significantly higher. Chemical pregnancy rate: 25/32 in the experimental group and 10/29 in the control group (letrozole) ($P=0.001$). Clinical pregnancy: 11/32 in the experimental group and 4/29 in the control group ($P=0.03$).
	In the acupuncture group (group I) there was a significant improvement in associated symptoms, compared to group II (bee stings) ($P=0.050$).
Dawood et al. ⁴⁴	In both groups, the levels of FSH and LH decreased, but they went down more in group II, and E2 increased, more in group II ($P<0.05$). The levels of AMH showed no significant differences in both groups ($P=0.388$). In the group of acupuncture, 13 women didn't become pregnant, but had regular menstruation, as well as 11 women in the group of bee stings ($P=0.361$). Pregnancy rate: 8 (5 in group 2 (bee stings) and 3 in the group of acupuncture) ($P=0.409$).
Qiu-Ping et al. ⁴⁹	Compared with the western medication group (letrozole), in the combined therapy group (letrozole combined with artificial cycle therapy with isolated ginger moxibustion (electroacupuncture + ginger moxibustion)), there was significant: reduction

in the symptom score of TCM ($P<0.01$); bilateral uterine pulse reduction ($P<0.01$); resistance index ($P<0.01$) and S/D optimization ($P<0.01$); greater number of ovulatory cycles ($P<0.01$); higher pregnancy rate; lower abortion rate.

The endometrial thickness was better in the combined therapy group ($P<0.01$).

Clinical pregnancy rate: 18/32 (combined therapy group) and 10/33 (western medication group) ($P<0.05$).

Early abortion rate: 1/18 (combined therapy group) and 5/10 (western therapy group) ($P<0.05$).

The live births were significantly higher in the clomiphene groups, compared to placebo groups (135/471 vs. 70/455). Between the active and control acupuncture, there were no significant differences (100/458 vs. 105/468).

Pregnancy rate: 74/235 (active acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 70/236 (control acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 33/223 (active acupuncture plus placebo group); 41/232 (control acupuncture plus placebo group) ($P=0.37$ between active acupuncture and clomiphene treatments).

Wu et al. ⁴⁶ Pregnancy loss/conception: 38/108 (active acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 37/106 (control acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 19/51 (active acupuncture plus placebo group); 16/55 (control acupuncture plus placebo group) ($P=0.51$ between active acupuncture and clomiphene treatments).

Live births: 69/235 (active acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 66/236 (control acupuncture plus clomiphene group); 31/223 (active acupuncture plus placebo group); 39/232 (control acupuncture plus placebo group) ($P=0.39$ between active acupuncture and clomiphene treatments).

Sex hormone level (E2, T, P, LH, and LH/FS) were significantly lower in the phytotherapy combined with the manual acupuncture group (MA group) ($P<0.05$). No significant improvement in FSH level or insulin resistance index. In the phytotherapy combined with the sham acupuncture group (SA group) only the progesterone was reduced ($P=0.008$).

Pan et al. ⁴⁷ The MA group had statistically significant improvement in the PCOS and TCM scores ($P<0.05$).

Ovulation rate: 75 (MA group, with 54 no ovulations) and 59 (SA group, with 70 no ovulations) ($P=0.046$).

Pregnancy rate: 19/41 (MA group) and 7/38 (SA group) ($P=0.008$).

In the observation group (clomiphene citrate capsules combined with heat-sensitive moxibustion), endometrial thickness increased significantly, and ovarian volume decreased ($P<0.05$). These results were also verified in the control group (clomiphene citrate capsules) but were better in the observation group ($P<0.05$).

Ye et al. ⁴⁸ The levels of serum hormones T and LH decreased in both groups but were lower in the observation group ($P<0.05$). The E2 also increased in both groups, but more in the moxibustion group ($P<0.05$).

The levels of immune inflammatory factor TNF- α and NF- κ B of the patients in both groups decreased, although were lower in the observation group ($P<0.05$).

Pregnancy rate: 7/35 (control group) and 17/33 (observation group) ($P<0.05$).

Regarding phytotherapy, the studies conducted by Duan *et al.* ⁴¹ and Hossein-Rashidi *et al.* ⁴³ demonstrated higher pregnancy rates in the groups that solely used phytotherapy compared to those using only medication. This finding suggests the effectiveness of phytotherapy in treating infertility. This results are in accordance with the results obtained in the Systematic Review by Ried *et al.* ³¹ in which they conclude that Traditional Chinese Herbal Medicine is more effective in the treatment of female infertility achieving on average a 60% pregnancy rate over 4 months compared with 30% achieved with standard Western Medical drug treatment, or IVF over 12 months. Additionally, Feng *et al.*'s ⁴² study combining phytotherapy with bromocriptine revealed higher pregnancy rates compared to the group using bromocriptine alone, indicating a potential benefit in combining phytotherapy with medication.

As for acupuncture, the study by Dawood *et al.* ⁴⁴ used acupuncture and bee stings and suggested that both interventions may promote symptom improvement and potentially aid in promoting pregnancy. However, the study did not present statistically significant results, possibly due to its small sample size ($n = 30$) and the absence of adaptation

of the acupoints according to the menstrual cycle. In contrast, Qiu-Ping et al.'s⁴⁵ study, comparing two groups using Letrozole alone versus Letrozole combined with electroacupuncture and moxibustion with ginger, demonstrated significant improvements in endometrial thickness, morphology, and uterine artery blood flow in patients with PCOS when combining approaches. This combined approach led to enhanced endometrial receptivity, increased clinical pregnancy rates, and reduced early abortion rates. On the other hand, Wu et al.'s⁴⁶ study did not support these findings and concluded that the use of acupuncture, with or without clomiphene, did not increase live births compared to control acupuncture and placebo. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fixed acupuncture protocol utilized throughout the menstrual cycle, similar to the study by Dawood *et al.*⁴⁴. These results emphasize the importance of customizing the acupuncture protocol and plant-based therapies according to the individual's menstrual cycle, as demonstrated in the studies by Duan *et al.*⁴¹, Qiu-Ping *et al.*⁴⁵ and Feng *et al.*⁴², which exhibited evidence of the benefit of the TCM techniques over other approaches.

In summary, the research on phytotherapy and acupuncture revealed promising outcomes in improving pregnancy rates, but also highlighted the significance of individualized treatment approaches to optimize their efficacy. The combination of TCM methods with conventional medication appears to offer potential benefits in some cases, emphasizing the value of integrated treatment strategies for infertility patients.

As well, the study conducted by Ye *et al.*⁴⁸ demonstrated the effectiveness of moxibustion when combined with clomiphene citrate in achieving a higher pregnancy rate compared to using clomiphene alone ($p < 0.05$). This finding suggests that moxibustion can complement and enhance the efficacy of conventional fertility medications, providing a potential benefit for women undergoing fertility treatments.

4.2. Other evaluations

Furthermore, beyond increasing the pregnancy rate, the TCM techniques have shown effectiveness in improving various parameters that are important predictors of female fertility. These parameters include levels of FSH, LH, E2, AMH, progesterone, ovarian stromal resistance, antral follicular count, ovarian diameter, and endometrial thickness. By positively influencing these physiological markers, these TCM treatments may support better ovarian function, hormonal balance, and overall reproductive health in women with infertility issues.

Moreover, the TCM methods have been found to impact ovulation rates positively, which is crucial for achieving successful conception. Additionally, the reduction in the number of miscarriages and premenstrual symptoms observed in some studies further underscores the potential benefits of the TCM techniques in promoting a healthy pregnancy and improving reproductive outcomes.

Feng *et al.*⁴², Qiu-Ping *et al.*⁴⁵ and Ye *et al.*⁴⁸ investigated the combination of the TCM modalities with specific medications—phytotherapy with bromocriptine, acupuncture with letrozole, and moxibustion with clomiphene, respectively. In all three studies, the groups that received a combination of TCM and medication showed statistically higher pregnancy rates ($p < 0.05$) compared to those using medication alone. These results suggest that integrating these TCM methods with conventional treatments may offer advantages in fertility enhancement.

Furthermore, Pan et al.'s⁴⁷ research comparing phytotherapy alone to its combined use with acupuncture revealed a statistically higher pregnancy rate in the group that received both therapies. This suggests that the synergistic effect of combining these two TCM modalities may be beneficial in enhancing fertility outcomes.

4.3. Intervention methodologies

The acupuncture points used in the studies on infertility treatment showed a certain level of consistency, with some variations observed in Dawood et al.'s⁴⁴ study. The most

commonly used points, found in four out of five articles, were CV6 (*Qi Hai*) and CV4 (*Guan Yuan*).

Guan Yuan (CV4) is a crucial acupuncture point located at the crossing of the Spleen Meridian, Kidney Meridian, Liver Meridian, and Conception Vessel. It is considered the "root of human" and holds the *Yuan-Primordial Qi*. The stimulation of this point has the effects of invigorating and reinforcing the *Yuan-Primordial Qi*, consolidating the constitution, and benefiting the Kidneys⁴⁸.

Qi Hai (CV6), known as the "Sea of *Qi*," is another frequently used point in these studies. It tonifies *Qi*, *Yang*, and *Yuan Qi*, with a specific focus on strengthening the Kidneys, especially Kidney *Yang*. In addition, it regulates and promotes *Qi* circulation, warms and invigorates the Lower and Middle *Jiao*, and removes *Qi* stagnation and Dampness^{61,62}.

The use of these points is particularly relevant in infertility cases where a Kidney deficiency is associated with Liver stagnation/deficiency, blood stagnation, or Spleen deficiency.

Other commonly used points, appearing in three articles, include CV3 (*Zhong Ji*), LR3 (*Tai Chong*), SP6 (*San Yin Jiao*), SP10 (*Xue Hai*), ST29 (*Gui Lai*), and EX-CA1 (*Zi Gong*). Points used in two articles include GV20 (*Bai Hui*), CV12 (*Zhong Wan*), LI4 (*He Gu*), ST25 (*Tian Shu*), ST36 (*Zu San Li*), KI3 (*Tai Xi*), and PC6 (*Nei Guan*). As well, the systematic review and meta-analysis of Gao *et al.*⁶³ suggest that CV3, CV4, CV6, ST36, SP6 and Ex-CA1 appeared to be the most frequently selected traditional acupuncture points for women with anovulatory infertility.

In general, the selected acupuncture points align with the underlying syndrome diagnosed in infertility conditions. The points chosen help regulate *Qi*, nourish and activate blood movement, nourish Kidney *Yin*, calm the Liver, and strengthen the Spleen^{61,62,64}.

It is worth noting that Dawood *et al.*'s⁴⁴ study deviated from the pattern observed in other articles, as they used acupoints that were substantially different. This variation in acupoint selection may contribute to the inconclusive results regarding acupuncture's efficacy compared to other articles that utilized more consistent acupoints. The significance of proper acupoint selection, along with the consideration of individualized treatment based on the patient's specific condition, highlights the importance of adapting the acupuncture protocol according to the menstrual cycle, as mentioned before.

In the studies that employed phytotherapy as a TCM technique for treating infertility, various herbal formulas were utilized, and some common plants were frequently included in these formulas. These plants include *Rizhoma dioscoreae* (*Shan Yao*), *Semen cuscutae* (*Tu Si Zi*), *Radix Paeoniae alba* (*Bai shao Yao*), and *Fructus corni* (*Shan Zhu Yu*).

These plants and their combinations are selected based on the TCM diagnosis of the patient's condition, particularly for tonifying the Kidney and activating blood circulation, for Spleen-Kidney *Yang* deficiency conditions or Liver – Kidney deficiency.

In general, these plants tonify the Spleen and Liver, Nourish *Yin* and Blood, Tonify Kidney *Yin*, strengthen Kidney *Yang*, astringes *Jing*, calm Liver *Yang* and Stabilize body fluids⁶⁵.

Timing Adaptation of the intervention methodology

The findings from Qiu-Ping *et al.*⁴⁵ emphasize the importance of adapting TCM treatment based on syndrome differentiation and the different stages of the menstrual cycle. The menstrual period is characterized by drastic changes in *Qi* and blood, highlighting the need to activate blood circulation and remove stasis. The removal of stasis contributes to the generation of fresh blood, which is beneficial for embryo implantation.

During the follicular phase, the treatment focuses on strengthening the Spleen, replenishing the Kidneys, and nourishing the blood, specifically to support follicular development and maturation. In the ovulation phase, the emphasis is on replenishing the Kidneys, promoting collateral circulation, smoothing Liver *Qi*, removing stagnation, and activating blood circulation. This phase aims to create an optimal environment for ovulation and conception.

Moving on to the luteal phase, there is an increase in *Yang Qi* and a consumption of *Yin*. Therefore, the treatment at this stage should focus on regulating and replenishing Kidney *Yang*, strengthening the Spleen, and promoting blood circulation. The goal during this phase is to warm the uterus and create a favorable environment for the implantation of the fertilized egg⁴⁵.

This approach highlights the significance of understanding the different stages of the menstrual cycle and tailoring the TCM treatment accordingly.

By adapting the treatment based on the menstrual cycle, TCM practitioners can address the specific needs and imbalances of each stage, optimizing the chances of successful pregnancy and enhancing overall reproductive health. This individualized and holistic approach aligns with the fundamental principles of TCM, where the goal is to restore balance and harmony within the body for improved health and well-being. However, it remains doubtful if this adaptation could be an aspect that should be considered, and studies that show significant differences are needed. For example, in Ried's⁶⁶ updated meta-analysis, it was founded that switching to an ovulation-stimulating herbal formula (Wen-Jing-Tang) for 8 weeks in a subgroup of 60 Japanese women with PCOS resulted in a marked increase in their ovulation rate (59%) compared to a subgroup of women which did not switch the formula (7%) ($p = 0.0036$). Clinical studies^{67,68} demonstrated that the formula had definite endocrinological effects on FSH, LH and estradiol favorable for ovulation.

4.4. Limitations

This review has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. Firstly, the number of studies included in our sample was relatively limited, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, except for the study by Wu *et al.*⁴⁶, most of the individual studies had small sample sizes, potentially impacting the statistical power and precision of the results.

Another important limitation is the lack of double-blind studies, which can introduce bias and affect the reliability of the outcomes. However, some methodological flaws in TCM research are common and are related to the specific characteristics of the therapeutic techniques⁶⁹. The short duration of the included studies and the limited follow-up time may also restrict our ability to assess the long-term effects of the TCM treatments on infertility.

Furthermore, some of the included studies lacked comprehensive information on treatment parameters, such as the exact timing of treatment initiation, the duration of treatment exposure, and the specific amounts of herbal formulas used. These details are crucial for understanding the treatment protocols and replicating the interventions in future research.

Moreover, an important aspect not addressed in most studies is the evaluation of male fertility, which could have a significant impact on the pregnancy rate results in both groups. The absence of male fertility assessment limits our understanding of the holistic effects of TCM treatments on infertility outcomes.

In summary, while this scoping review provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy for treating infertility, it is essential to acknowledge these limitations when interpreting the findings. Future studies should aim to address these shortcomings to strengthen the evidence base and provide more robust conclusions regarding the potential benefits of these TCM approaches in infertility management.

4.5. Final remarks

In light of the data obtained from this scoping review, it is evident that acupuncture, phytotherapy, moxibustion, and electropuncture are common TCM methods used for the

treatment of infertility. The findings indicate that their efficacy is further enhanced when combined with certain medications or with each other.

Among the various acupoints and plants utilized in the studies, CV4 and CV6 were the most frequently employed acupoints. These points hold significance in addressing Kidney deficiency syndrome, which is commonly associated with infertility conditions. Additionally, the consistent use of *Rizhoma dioscoreae* (Shan Yao), *Semen cuscutae* (Tu Si Zi), *Radix Paeoniae alba* (Bai shao Yao), and *Fructus corni* (Shan Zhu Yu) in the phytotherapy formulations points to their importance in tonifying the Spleen and Liver, nourishing Yin and Blood, strengthening Kidney Yang, and stabilizing body fluids – all of which play critical roles in improving fertility.

It is essential to emphasize that the selection of acupoints and herbal formulas should be tailored to the specific syndrome diagnosis and menstrual cycle of each individual patient. This individualized approach is fundamental in maximizing the effectiveness of TCM treatments for infertility and ensuring a holistic and targeted management.

Overall, the findings of this review support the potential of acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy as valuable therapeutic options for infertility treatment. However, it is vital to recognize that more research with larger sample sizes, longer study durations, and rigorous study designs is necessary to establish conclusive evidence regarding the benefits of these TCM techniques in infertility management. Moreover, future studies should strive to address the limitations identified in this review to strengthen the reliability and applicability of the findings.

5. Conclusion

The current evidence suggests that acupuncture, moxibustion and phytotherapy hold promise as effective interventions for infertility. Their combined use with medications or among different TCM modalities may offer additional advantages. Moving forward, a patient-centered approach, considering individual characteristics and specific syndromes, will be critical in optimizing treatment outcomes in the context of infertility management with TCM techniques.

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